

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B164
Date: 28 Jan 2006
Take Off 09:41:16
Landing: 12:26:47
Flight Time 2h45m31

Campaign: DABEX (Cirrus)
Trials Instructions: Neon
Operating Area: Niamey Airfield

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Wet Neph	Martin Glew	Met Office
9	IR camera	Joss Kent	Met Office
10	Filters / camerawoman	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
11	Aircraft Scientist 1	Ellie Highwood	University of Reading
12	Aircraft Scientist 2	Simon Osborne	Met Office
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Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b164
 Date: 28 Jan 2006
 Project: DABEX NEON
 Location: Niamey Airfield

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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082842		Position	0.72 kft	316	13'28.65N, 2'10.53E
092727		INU	0.71 kft	316	Set to Navigate
092837		Heimann	0.71 kft	316	Shutter Open
093123		Heimann	0.71 kft	316	Cal, 30-40deg
094015		Heimann	0.71 kft	296	Shutter Closed
094116		T/O	1.2 kft	090	Niamey
094644	094958	Profile 1	5.0 - 2.3 kft	286	
094800		Videos	2.4 kft	095	Start FFC & DFC
095155	095428	Profile 1	2.2 - 0.76 kft	094	To 50'
095428	095635	Profile 2	0.76 - 1.9 kft	090	Ovhd Niamey
095823	100251	Profile 2	2.0 - 6.0 kft	267	
100437	101102	Profile 2	6.0 - 12.0 kft	094	
101301	101441	Profile 3	12.0 - 10.7 kft	251	
101441	101809	Run 1.1	10.7 kft	231	Offset 2.3nm
101557		Event	10.7 kft	243	Abeam end r/w
102031	102411	Run 1.2	10.7 kft	067	Missed r/w
102134		Event	10.7 kft	074	Abeam end r/w
102609	102934	Run 1.3	10.7 kft	234	Good
102715		Event	10.7 kft	241	Abeam end r/w
103150	103353	Run 1.4	10.7 kft	074	Far end r/w only
103253		Event	10.7 kft	067	Abeam end r/w
103353	103940	Profile 4	10.7 - 5.7 kft	065	
104127	104817	Run 2.1	5.7 kft	241	Offset 1nm, ok@start
104719		Event	5.7 kft	247	Abeam end r/w
105159	105426	Run 2.2	5.7 kft	068	Good @ end
105304		Event	5.7 kft	066	Abeam end r/w
105749	110032	Run 2.3	5.7 kft	251	Good @ start
105945		Event	5.7 kft	246	Abeam end r/w
110422	110637	Run 2.4	5.7 kft	074	Good @ end
110553		Event	5.7 kft	068	Abeam end r/w
110706	110945	Profile 5	5.7 - 3.7 kft	091	
111216	111520	Run 3.1	3.7 kft	255	Offset 0.6nm
111447		Event	3.7 kft	244	Abeam end r/w
111547		Videos	3.7 kft	267	Change tapes
111920	112132	Run 3.2	3.7 kft	074	Offset 0.7nm
112053		Event	3.7 kft	072	Abeam end r/w
112515	112725	Run 3.3	3.7 kft	243	Offset 0.67nm
112554		Event	3.7 kft	243	Abeam end r/w
113108	113335	Run 3.4	3.7 kft	079	Offset 0.65nm
113317		Event	3.7 kft	066	Abeam r/w
113402	113606	Profile 6	3.7 - 1.7 kft	091	
113812	114049	Run 4.1	1.8 - 1.7 kft	250	Offset 0.23nm, Q1013
114018		Event	1.7 kft	249	Abeam end r/w
114428	114638	Run 4.2	1.8 - 1.7 kft	071	
114609		Event	1.7 kft	066	Abeam end r/w
115003	115151	Run 4.3	1.7 - 1.8 kft	232	
115116		Event	1.7 kft	236	Abeam end r/w
115510	115713	Run 4.4	1.7 kft	074	
115642		Event	1.7 kft	067	Abeam end r/w
115713	120549	Profile 7	1.7 - 10.0 kft	066	
120741	121400	Profile 7	10.0 - 16.0 kft	239	
121844		ASPs	8.5 kft	244	Closed
122647		Land	0.76 kft	087	Niamey
122731		Heimann	0.76 kft	088	Shutter open
123327		Heimann	0.78 kft	317	Shutter Closed
123424		Position	0.78 kft	317	13'28.65N, 2'10.53E

B164 Track 28-JAN-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DABEX: local race-track sampling over Niamey

Flight No: B164 (cirrus)

Date: 28 January 2006

Trial objectives:

If Cirrus is present, then to determine the effect of mineral dust on the IRC imagery.

Location:

Over local area close to Niamey (13.54°N, 2.66°E).

Weather:

High loadings of mineral dust preferred, but not essential.

Special requirements:

Missed approach (50ft) over Niamey airfield and low-level (500ft) flying over land.

Flight pattern (cirrus present):

1. Take off from Niamey [10:10Z].
2. Taxi along runway at low speed with Heimann operating.
3. Ascend to 5000ft and carry out a missed approach descent to 50ft over Niamey airfield [15mins, T=15mins].
4. Broken profile ascent from 50ft to FL150 (or above the dust layer), at a rate of 1000ft/min with turns at 2000ft, FL60, and FL100 [20mins, T=35mins].
5. Racetrack over the airport for two complete circuits at FL147 [20mins, T=55mins].
6. Broken profile descent at 1000ft/minute with turn at FL100 to maintain position of the aircraft close to airfield to FL57 [15mins, T=70mins].
7. Racetrack over the airport for two complete circuits at FL57 [20mins, T=90mins].
8. Profile descent at 1000ft/minute to FL37 [5mins, T=95mins].
9. Racetrack over the airport for two complete circuits at FL37 [20mins, T=115mins].
10. Profile descent at 1000ft/minute to FL17 [5mins, T=120mins].
11. Racetrack over the airport for two complete circuits at FL17 [20mins, T=140mins].
12. Recover aircraft position to landing (long landing with slow taxi) [T=150mins].

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet

Flight B164

28th January 2006

Summary of the weather conditions:

Huge area of thick cirrus to the north and west, moving in a northeasterly flow within the upper jet. Bottom fringe of this cirrus within the Niamey region. Lots of medium level (altocumulus) cloud over and to the south of Niamey. This latter cloud largely broke during the day and was only very patchy during the flight.

Points defined:

Niamey airfield only (13°29'N, 2°10'E). 700ft elevation.

Summary of the flight:

A successful flight was carried out to test the application of the infrared camera with atmospheric loadings of dust aerosol over Niamey airfield. LIDAR imagery before flight revealed the medium level cloud to be between FL140 and FL150, so it was decided that the upper level of our initial climb was to be FL120. The French ultra-light aircraft with its downward looking LIDAR operated today in the near-vicinity at just below cloud at ~FL140. A standard missed approach profile was carried out to 50ft followed by a climb to FL120, with interrupts at 2000ft, FL060 and FL100 to keep the profile constrained in distance. This profile showed two dust layers below 6000ft and a high level aged biomass burning layer; the top of this layer was above FL120. The first set of two racetracks (across the runway at ~30 degs) was performed at FL107 above all the dust aerosol but within the aged biomass burning aerosol plume i.e. four runs (R1.1-R1.4) were carried out. Further similar sets of racetracks were carried out at FL057 (just within tops of dust), 3700ft (within dust) and 1700ft (within dust). A good level of success was achieved with getting the runway within the field of view of the IR camera. PCASP concentrations within the dust aerosol were 300-500/cc, within the aged biomass burning aerosol PCASP concs were 500-1000/cc. Ozone depletion was observed within the dust at low level and the usual pattern of nephelometer scattering with wavelength clearly identified the different aerosol types. A final profile ascent was made to FL160 from 1700ft at 1000ft/min all the way with an interrupt at FL100. The top of the biomass burning aerosol was just at the top of the climb; the thickness of this aerosol layer was about 6000ft with fairly constant loading/nephelometer scattering with height. 3-6/8 of cirrus cloud was above throughout the sortie.

Flight B164 12:17:57

Heading 246 deg Speed 269 knots Height 9.5kft Press 708mb

Lat 13.3N Long 2.0E Wind 5 ms-1/ 107 deg

Temp 10.63C Dewpoint -7.15C

From 11:28:36 to now

Current values

++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	9.58	Kft	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	-0.9	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	-0.9	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
++++	NEPH RED SP	-0.9	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....164.....

Date28/1/2006.....

Page1 of ...4...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:30 GMT	pre flight t/o				altos clouds ~ 14 kft broken + clearing thru morning.
09:40 GMT					Slow taxi off centre line to t/o.
09:42 GMT					t/o.
					5000' at base to top of dust
09:46:44 GMT					profile 1 start to missed approach.
09:49:58					end profile 1 descent at 2300 ft.
09:51:58					recommencing profile descent 1.
09:54:28					end of profile 1 start profile 2 (50 ft) missed approach
09:58:23					profile 2 recommenced at 2000 ft
					Visible to ^{aerosol} layer to 5kft
					200 m' from ground to 3kft then falls away.
10:02:51					interrupt profile 2. at 6000 ft.
10:04:37					start profile 2 again to 10000 ft
10:06:53					continue to FL120 as this heading
10:11:02					end profile 2 at FL120 10:11:02
10:30:01					profile descent to 10770L
					Profile 3
					12 10 5
					base
					dust
					dust
					No ground in scat coord
					100 40 200 m'

60

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**.....64.....

 Date28/1/2006.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:14:41					end profile 3 start of run 1.1 FL107
					run 1.1 race track log over a field
					Some light cirrus
					run 1.1 all OK IR sensor OK.
10:18:09					end of run 1.1
10:20:31					run 1.2 start @ FL107.
					run 1.2 saw very off. 1.1 spot on.
10:24:11					end of run 1.2 @ FL108
					profile descent to FL57.
					cirrus ~ 3/8. little stratocumulus
					run 1.3 start. FL107
10:28					O ₃ + CO ₂ - weakly correlated in both dust layers and ^{visibly} correlated in biomass.
10:29:34					end of run 1.3 spot on run.
10:31:50					start of run 1.4 possibly saw end of the run.
10:33:53					end of run 1.4 start of profile FL57
10:39:40					end of profile FL57
					smaller scattering signal but broader biomass layer at lower alt on descent to top of dust layer at FL57.
					Visibly biomass layer darker and sat directly at top of ^{later} dust layer
10:41:37					Start of 2.1 FL57
10:48:18					end of 2.1 FL57
10:51:59					Start of 2.2 FL57

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.164**.....

Date28/1/2006.....

Page ...3... of ...4...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:27:26		FL57			end of run 2.2 at FL57
					On descent from FL107 to FL57 low biomass to 8km the broad layer from FL80 to FL57 continues to top of dust.
10:57:49	run 2.3	FL57	250		Start of run 2.3
11:00:00	run 2.3	FL57	250		end of run 2.3
11:02:22	run 2.4	FL57	66		Start run 2.4.
11:06:37	run 2.4	FL57	66		end of run 2.4
11:07:06	profile desc		93		start of profile descent. (profile 5) 2.2 and 2.3 good view at start 2.3 and 2.4 good view at end
11:09:45	P.d. desc	FL37	84		end profile descent 5 at FL37
11:12:16	Run 3.1	FL37	252		start of run 3.1 Skill in dust layer similar scatt coeff as FL57
					Descent Profile

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B164**.....

Date **28/1/2006**.....

Page **4**... of **4**...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:15:20	RUN 3.1	FL37	250		end of run 3.1 ^{Human seen some of runway} at bottom of image
11:19:20	RUN 3.2	FL37	67		run 3.2 start too far away on run
11:21:32	RUN 3.2	FL37	67		end of 3.2
11:25:15	RUN 3.3	FL37	236		start of 3.3 ^{Aerosol} Scattering layer and more FL37 variable at this level than 4.
11:27:25	RUN 3.3	FL37	240		end of 3.3 Spot on for IR. @ 0.67 ^{at 1000m}
11:31:08	RUN 3.4	FL37	70		start 3.4
11:33:25	RUN 3.4	FL37	20		end 3.4 Spot on for IR.
11:36:06	PROFILE 6	FL17			end profile 6 ^{scatt coeff} considering profile at E end ~150 m ⁻¹ dust
11:38:12	RUN 4.1	FL17	250		start of run. Spot on IR
11:40:49	RUN 4.1	FL17	250		end of run. Scat coeff inc to 200 m ⁻¹ at E end of run
11:44:28	RUN 4.2	FL17	64		start of run. good view for IR
11:46:38	RUN 4.2	FL17	65		end of run. Scat coeff inc to 200 m ⁻¹
11:50:03	RUN 4.3	FL17	252		start of run. good view for IR
11:51:51	RUN 4.3	FL17	255		end of run
11:55:10	RUN 4.4	FL17	68		start of run. IR camera good.
11:57:13	RUN 4.4	FL17	68		end of run. Scat coeff still ~200 m ⁻¹
11:57:13	PROFILE 7	FL17 (at start)	65		start of profile to FL150, break to made + return.
12:05:49	PROFILE 7	FL100	65		Profile break FL100 ^{Strong biomass} layer on top of dust
12:07:41	PROFILE 7	FL100	244	Profile restart	Profile end @ FL150 ^{7 ad 8 left} He clear
12:41:00	PROFILE 7	FL160	244		return to airfield ^{then further} biomass above

Inco sketches
FFSSR sketch of but all other cloud physics OK.
reph cut reph of col
Ams OK.
IR camera OK.

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: 3164

Date: 28/1/2006 RE PROCESSED BY S OSBORNE 13/3/06

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	✓	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	✓	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	✓	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	✓	Note the calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	✓	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto 10s
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	✓	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		???. can't make head nor tail as yet.
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B164

Date: 28/11/2006

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	✓	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	✓	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	✓	
4) Log on to FLOODS	✓	
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	✓	
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat iii) exit	✓	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	✓	NO AUX file!
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

<p>Preparation of imagery for Core data product</p> <p>iii) WAVE> auto_image</p> <p>a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:</p> <p>b) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD</p> <p>d) Enter start time 0 if unknown</p> <p>e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown</p> <p>f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10</p> <p>iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files</p>	<p>PMSDATA:</p>	<p>FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS</p>
<p>ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC</p>		
<p>Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter</p>		
<p>Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files</p>		
<p>9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>b) Directory: PMSDATA:</p> <p>c) File generation: Hit enter</p> <p>d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data</p>		
<p>e) TAS: Y</p> <p>f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX</p> <p>g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty</p> <p>h) Start time: 0 if unknown</p> <p>i) End time: 240000 if unknown</p> <p>j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5</p> <p>k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown</p> <p>l) Coefficient choice: 2</p> <p>m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>Note the particle type</p>
<p>10) In PVWAVE</p> <p>i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'</p> <p>Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!</p> <p>ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'</p> <p>iii) exit</p>		
<p>11) MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D</p> <p>b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX</p> <p>c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name</p> <p>d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		
<p>12) CHECKS:</p>		
<p>i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?</p>		

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.164**.....

 Date **28/01/2006**

 Operator's name: **M. GLEW**.....

 Page **1** of **3**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
Pre-flight, Zeroed both nephs. Wet neph "clean" data collection wandering alot. Several zeroes of wet neph (med. problem persists).								
Before take off labview talking to nephs OK in same configuration as end of labr flight. Chiller serial cable not connected. W/O ratios 0.75 - 0.8 with colour separation. Wet RH 45%, Dry 20%.								
0945 labview fell over during take off but recovered straight away - talking to both nephs -								
0958	A2	1900'	10.3	14%	38%	Chiller Dry.		
1005	P2 ^{interact}	FL063	10.2	11%	35%	Chiller Silled but switched off		
1010	P2	FL117	10.2	10%	35%	Chiller off, Nothing on trap.		
1012	-ve wet neph scattering in Blue - $-8E-6$. Dry neph + 60							
101441	R1.1	FL107	10.2	10%	43%	30°C	Chiller to +35°C. (in) 30°C	
1016	R1.1	"	10.2	10%	47%	↑	Chiller to +43°C. Blue scattering -ve.	
101804	R1.1a	"	10.1	9%	61%	↑	Chiller at +43°C Green scattering -ve. Red +ve.	
102031	I.2	FL107	10.2	9%	65%	↑	Chiller to +45°C	
102341	R1.2a	FL107	10.2	10%	73%	45°C	Chiller at +45°C, RH maxed at 73%.	
102604	R1.3	FL107	10.1	10%	75%	45°C	Chiller at +45°C, -ve green + blue scattering.	
1028	R1.3	FL107	10.1	9%	75%	↓	Chiller to +44°C	
102934	R1.3a	FL107	10.2	10%	73%	↓	Chiller at +44°C	
103150	R1.4	FL107	10.2	8%	72%	↓	Chiller at +43°C	

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B/64**.....

 Date 28/01/2006

 Operator's name: M. GLEW.....

 Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1032	1.4	FL107	10.2	4%	69%	↓		Chiller at +41°C
103353	1.4	FL607	10.2	8%	68%	—		chiller off for profile.
104127	R2.1	FL057	10.1	9%	63%	↓		chiller to +38°C. Blue 7 SE-6 green 3E-5 red 4 SE-5
1043	R2.1	FL057	10.2	9%	62%	↑		Chiller to +41°C
10445	R2.1	FL057	10.2	10%	67%			chiller at +41°C
1045	R2.1	FL057	10.2	11%	68%	↑		Chiller to +43°C
1047	R2.1	FL057	10.2	11%	72%	↑		Chiller to +45°C
105154	R2.2	FL057	10.2	7%	77%	—		Chiller at +45°C. RH moved at 78%
1053	R2.2	FL057	10.4	12%	78%	↓		Chiller to +42°C
105426	R2.2	FL057	10.4	12%	73%	↓		chiller at +42°C
1055	—	FL057	10.4	11%	73%	↓		Chiller to +40°C for R2, w/Dratins B0.2, G0.35, R0.5
105749	R2.3	FL057	10.3	12%	69%	↓		Chiller to +25°C
110032	R2.3	FL057	10.4	11%	56%	↓	+29°C	
1101	—	FL057	10.3	7%	49%	↑	+27°C	chiller to +35°C
110422	R2.4	FL057	10.4	8%	55%	↑	+35°C	Chiller to +45°C. Trap clear.
110637	R2.4	FL057	10.3	11%	70%	—		chiller off for profile.
111216	R3.1	FL057	10.0	5%	75%	↑		Chiller to +45°C R4E5, G3E-5, B15E-5
111520	R3.1	FL037	10.1	7%	78%	—		Chiller at +45°C. RH moved 78%
111700	—	FL037	10.2	6%	78%	↓		Chiller to +38°C
111920	R3.2	FL037	10.3	8%	66%	↑		Chiller to +45°C

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B164

Date:

29 JAN 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 µm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
Except for				

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B164Q7	----	----	Top	10:14:41	10:33:53	R1.1/R1.2/R1.3/R1.4	1555	FL107, old biomass
Filters run1	B164N7	----	----	Bottom	10:14:41	10:33:53	R1.1/R1.2/R1.3/R1.4	1137	FL107, old biomass
Filters run2	B164Q8	----	----	Top	10:39:40	11:06:37	R2.1/R2.2/R2.3/R2.4	3107	FL057, just at the top of the dust layer, background
Filters run2	B164N8	----	----	Bottom	10:39:40	11:06:37	R2.1/R2.2/R2.3/R2.4	2108	FL057, just at the top of the dust layer, background
Filters run3	B164Q9	----	----	Top	11:12:16	11:33:35	R3.1/R3.2/R3.3/R3.4	2442	FL037, dust layer
Filters run3	B164N9	----	----	Bottom	11:12:16	11:33:35	R3.1/R3.2/R3.3/R3.4	1789	FL037, dust layer
Filters run4	B164Q10	----	----	Top	11:38:12	11:57:13	R4.1/R4.2/R4.3/R4.4	2607	FL017, dust layer
Filters run4	B164N10	----	----	Bottom	11:38:12	11:57:13	R4.1/R4.2/R4.3/R4.4	1704	FL017, dust layer

IIR Camera Log

Page 1 of

Flight No: 13164

Campaign: DABEX

Date: 28/1/06

Operator: Joss.

Fitted lens: 100mm
Camera angle: -35°C

20° to runway

Start Time	Stop Time	Height	Lat	Long	Remarks
093641	094006	MAXI			1 sec data of runway.
095310	095443	Missed	Approach		
101603	101636	FL07	R1.1		Good view of runway
102150	102219	FL07	R1.2	2-3Nm	No view - too far away from runway
102724	102758	FL107	R1.3	offset.	Good views again
103323	103351	FL107	R1.4	1Nm	End of runway in view
104725	104749	FL57	R2.1	offset.	Good runway view at start
105317	105349	FL57	R2.2	"	Runway view at end of run.
105946	110019	FL57	R2.3	"	Runway view at start of run
110606	110638	FL57	R2.4	"	Runway view at end of run
111449	111513	FL37	R3.1	offset.	Runway just started at start
111449		FL37	R3.2	offset.	Total miss
112653	112718	FL37	R3.3	"	Good views at start again
113312	113337	FL37	R3.4	"	Good run - mid runway view
114014	114036	1700'	R4.1	offset	Good crossing view
114614	114640	1700'	R4.2	= 0.23 n.m.	" " "
115134	115150	1700'	R4.3	"	" " "
115650	115704	1700'	R4.2	"	" " "
122746	122824	Grnd			Runway ramp on ground

B164 IR Camera Calibration

Active NUC = 050126-NUC3

BPM Filename = DIBTEST1

Source Ref: cold temp = 15°C
Hot temp = 45°C

Thermometer check
Aircraft ~~At~~ Normal.
73.1 72.5
7.6°C 7.5°C

Time 082140 Temp Cold ~~6.8~~ 6.8°C Temp Hot 80.5°C

Files

Time 082417 7.0°C 78°C

Aircraft Thermoin cold
Mercury Thermo in hot

Files

Time 082620 7.2°C 76°C

Files

Time 082900 7.3 72.8

Post Flight

Time 125740 6.8 75.5°C

Aircraft Thermo in cold
Mercury Thermo in hot

125940 6.7 73.5

130140 6.5 71.2

Thermo check.

Aircraft Normal

6.9°C 6.5°C

69.4 68.8

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 164

Date: 28th January 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	N
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B164

Date: 28th January 2006

Instruments

1. JW – not zeroing, as on recent flights.
2. Flight Manager's pc locked up in flight. Rebooted then okay.

Cloud Physics – PCASP ok

FFSSP- switched off at low level,

2DC – noisy towards end of flight,

SID 2 noisy on occasions, otherwise ok

Core Chemistry – Ok

AMS – ok

Wet Neph – Unable to zero wet neph, green & blue channels showing negative values

IR Camera – ok

Not fitted: ARIES, MARSS, DEIMOS

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls - Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B164:

Log	Reason
None	

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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